

A Study on the Quality of After Sales Service in Honda Coimbatore

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of this study is to check the quality of after sales service attributes in Honda Coimbatore and the customer satisfaction levels through the services. This study is a quantitative research type with a sample of 100 respondents and data had been collected through a structured questionnaire. Statistical tools applied are Simple Percentage analysis, chi-square. From the study it is revealed that the dealer has to be little more assertive and attractive in their service no matter whether it's financial schemes. Sales promotions are excellent. More awareness should be created with the customer's regarding product utility. It is hoped that the finding and suggestion would enable the dealer to understand the performance level and other grey areas where things will have to be consolidated to hold a better market position.

KEYWORDS: statistical tool, sales promotion

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INTRODUCTION:

In a context of global competition and decreasing profits from product sales, the after-sales services and activities (i.e. those taking place after the purchase of the product and devoted to support customers in the usage and disposal of goods) constitute a relevant profit source as well as a key differentiator for manufacturing companies and resellers. Profit generated by after-sales services is often higher than the one obtained with sales; the service market can be four or five times larger than the market for products and it may generate at least three times the turnover of the original purchase during a given product's life-cycle. It is estimated that service networks in only four US industries could generate revenues of \$6 billion to \$8 billion a year from after sales service, parts, and products. Besides being a long-term potential revenue source, the after-sales service constitutes a mean to uncover customer needs and a strategic driver for customer retention. It represents, in fact, "one of the few constant connections that customers have with a brand" influencing customer satisfaction and loyalty. Finally, after sales service is a way to allow a continuous improvement of product design and quality. The perception of after-sales as a source of competitive advantage and business opportunity requires a shift from a traditional product-centric view, in which after-sales is considered a "necessary evil", to a customer-centric view.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Herbig & Palumbo (1993) Emphasized the different conditions of the after-sales markets in the Eastern and

Western perspectives. It is very strange in the Eastern market in their findings. Although the Japanese customers would not like to show their patience and are eager to have a high efficient after-sales service, most of Japanese manufacturers stick to control the after-sales service by their own departments or their own subsidiaries. By contrast that in the Western market, especially in the North American market, the manufacturers has trends to ask their dealers to process the after-sales service, though the customers seem more reasonable to accept the working slow down such as the idle time and waiting time during the service. One possible reason to explain this phenomenon is that Japan is a small place by its area of land. So the manufacturers can easily cover this market by their own capacity. For example, the manufacturer itself has enough repair force to cover the whole Japanese areas. But the North America is a huge land that if one manufacturer wants to manage the after-sales service by itself, it needs to invest and spend a lot on the service capacity.

Wilson, Boström, & Lundin (1999), the after-sales service might be cut into pieces according to the functions. And there need to design an optimal way to determine the responsibilities for the service tasks. Hence, by utilizing the QFD modeling the later sections, we are able to detect the details conditions of the Chinese market and also know the rational ways for developing this market.

Cohen, Agrawal, & Agrawal (2006) found that in the industries like automobiles, white goods, industrial machinery and information technology, companies have sold so many units over the years that their after-sales market have become four to five times larger than the original equipment business. No doubt that the after-sales service business will be the superstar business for the industries with listed above. Compared the marketing job which mainly focuses on selling and the promoting the current products or service. The after-sales service job takes care of the entire sold ones since the company started its business. Furthermore, after-sales service brings companies with lots of profits in high margin business.

Cohen, Agrawal, & Agrawal (2006) also thought that customers don't expect products to be perfect but they do expect manufacturers to fix things quickly when they break down. This is obvious in the customer's mind. Especially in the industrial machinery industry, customers are more eager to get good performance on after-sales service.

Shanmugaraja, Nataraj, & Gunasekaran (2010) pointed out that the very existence of business depends on customer satisfaction. Customer expects high quality after-sales services, even willing to pay premium for better service. From customer perspective, good after-sales service quality leads to long-term customers relationships measured by repatronage and cross sales, also customer recommend the service to others. So if the after-sales service can clear up the customers' dissatisfaction, there would be more marketing opportunities for the company. Selene & Schemers (2001) stated that successful service design and development requires a systematic approach that links and interfaces with a comprehensive set of customer needs, their translation into various service attributes, and the development of a properly designed service process. One of the systematic tools for making the above links is quality function deployment (QFD), which has been adapted for service environments. And this method is going to be used in this thesis to detect how to build an efficient after-sales service model to achieve customers' requirements. Mazur (2008) illustrated that QFD's strength is in creating positive value and preventing negative quality before it is designed into downstream processes where it is much more expensive to correct. So I will cooperate with a project team from the case company X to work together to investigate the customers' needs and to build the QFD process. The introduction of how to collect data and how to use the QFD model will be explained in the following methodology part.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

A. Primary objective:

- To study the quality of after-sales service offered by HONDA Automobiles

B. Secondary objective

- To study the after sales and service of the dealer
- To study the convenience of the location of the service station
- To study the timeliness of service
- To study whether they use genuine spare parts
- To study whether the dealer is customer friendly and their friendly delivery.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Descriptive Research

Descriptive Research- descriptive research includes surveys and the facts finding enquiry of different kinds. The major purpose of descriptive research is description of the state of affairs as it exists as present.

The main characteristic of this method is that is that the researcher has no control over the variables; he can only report what has happened or what is happening.

DATA COLLECTION METHODS

➤ **Primary data**

Data collection in Coimbatore will be collected through the questionnaire method.

➤ **Sampling unit**

The study is carried out only in Coimbatore city.

➤ **Sampling size**

The sample size was 100.

➤ **Sampling Method**

The method followed was simple random sampling.

TOOLS USED FOR THE STUDY

- Simple percentage analysis
- Chi - Square test

SIMPLE PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS

Percentage refers to a special kind of ratio. Percentage is used for making a comparison of two or more series of data.

Formula

$$\frac{\text{Number of respondents}}{\text{Total number of respondents}} \times 100$$

CHI-SQUARE ANALYSIS

The Chi-square Test is an important test amongst the several tests of significance adopted by the statisticians. Chi-square is a statistical measure used in sampling analysis for comparing a theoretical variance. It is calculated using the SPSS 17.0 package by choosing Analyze=====> Non-Parametric Test=====> Chi-Square Test.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATIONS

The data collected through various sources have been analyzed in the following pages.

PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS

TABLE-1 SHOWING AGE OF RESPONDENT

AGE	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
20-30 YEARS	36	36
31-40 YEARS	20	20
41-50 YEARS	19	19
51-60 YEARS	12	12
Above 60	13	13
TOTAL	100	100

Source: Primary Data

INTERPRETATION

The above table shows that 36% of respondents are between 20-30 years of age, 20% are between 31-40 years, 19% are between 40-50 years, 12% are between 50-60 years, and 13% are between above 60 years of age.

TABLE-2 SHOWING GENDER OF RESPONDENTS

Gender	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
MALE	75	75
FEMALE	25	25
TOTAL	50	100

Source: Primary Data

INTERPRETATION:

The above table shows that 75% of respondents are male and 25% of respondents are female.

TABLE-3 SHOWING THE QUALIFICATION OF THE RESPONDENTS

Education Qualification	No Of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Up to 12 th	41	41
Diploma	23	23
Ug	19	19
Pg	17	17
Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

INTERPRETATION:

From the above table it is interpreted that 41% of respondents were upto 12th, and 23% of respondents were diploma and 19% of respondents were graduate and remaining 17% of respondents were postgraduate.

TABLE-4 SHOWING THE ANNUAL INCOME OF THE RESPONDENTS

Annual income	Frequency	Percent
below 2lakhs	40	40
2-5 lakhs	46	46
above 5 lakhs	14	14
Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

INTERPRETATION:

From the above table it is interpreted it is interpreted that 46% of respondents annual income were between 2-5 lakhs, 40% of the respondents annual income were below 2 lakhs and 14% of the respondents annual income were above 5 lakhs.

TABLE-5 SHOWING THE RESIDENCE OF THE RESPONDENTS

Residence	Frequency	Percent
within the city	63	63
outside the city	37	37
Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

INTERPRETATION:

From the above table it is interpreted that 63% of the respondents were within the city and 37% of the respondents were outside the city.

TABLE-6 SHOWING TOTAL TIME TAKEN OF THE RESPONDENTS

Total time taken	Frequency	Percent
Highly satisfied 2min()	22	22
Satisfied (2-5min)	36	36
Neutral (5-10min)	27	27
Dissatisfied 15 min()	10	10
Highly dissatisfied 20min()	5	5
Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

INTERPRETATION:

From the above table it is interpreted that 36% of the respondents were satisfied with the total time taken and 27% of the respondents were neutral with the total time taken and 22% of the respondents were highly satisfied with the total time taken and 10% of the respondents were dissatisfied with the total time taken and 5% of the respondents were highly dissatisfied with the total time taken.

TABLE-7 SHOWING THE COMPANY PROVIDE FREE SERVICES

Free Services	Frequency	Percent
Monthly	14	14
Half yearly	66	66
Yearly	15	15
Quarterly	5	5
Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

INTERPRETATION:

From the above table it is interpreted that 66% of the company provides free service in half yearly and 15% of the company provides were free service in yearly taken and 22% of and 14% of the company provides were free service in monthly and 5% of the company provides free service in quarterly wise.

TABLE-8 SHOWING COMPANY TAKING CARE OF INSURANCE POLICY FOR VECHILES

Insurance policy	Frequency	Percent
Strongly agree	31	31
Agree	20	20
Neutral	32	32
Dis agree	10	10
Strongly disagree	7	7
Total	100	100

Source: primary data

INTERPRETATION:

From the above table it is interpreted that 32% of the respondents were neutral with the taking care of insurance policy and 31% of the respondents were strongly agree with the taking care of insurance policy and 20% of the respondents were agree with the taking care of insurance policy and 10% of the respondents were disagree with the taking care of insurance policy and 7% of the respondents were strongly disagree with the taking care of insurance policy.

TABLE-9 SHOWING THE RESPONDENTS FOR THE CUSTOMERS CARE CALL CENTERS

Call Centers	Frequency	Percent
Highly satisfied	28	28
Satisfied	33	33
Neutral	16	16
Dissatisfied	13	13
Highly dissatisfied	10	10
Total	100	100

Source: primary data

INTERPRETATION:

From the above table it is interpreted that 33% of the respondents were satisfied with the customer care call

centers and 28% of the respondents were highly satisfied with the customer care call centers and 16% of the respondents were neutral with the customer care call centers and 13% of the respondents were dissatisfied with the customer care call centers and 10% of the respondents were highly dissatisfied with customer care call centers.

TABLE-10 SHOWING THE EXPERIENCE RELATED TO AVAILABILITY OF SPARE PARTS

Availability of Spare part	Frequency	Percent
Easily availability	38	38
Some time availability	40	40
Rarely availability	19	19
Not availability	3	3
Total	100	100

Source: primary data

INTERPRETATION:

From the above table it is interpreted that 40% of the respondents were some time availability in showroom and 38% of the respondents were easily availability in showroom and 19% of the respondents were rarely availability in showroom and 3% of the respondents were not availability in showroom.

TABLE-11 SHOWING THE CUSTOMER SATISFICATION OF THE DOOR DELIVERY

Door delivery	Frequency	Percent
Highly satisfied	18	18
Satisfied	58	58
Neutral	12	12
Dissatisfied	2	2
Highly dissatisfied	10	10
Total	100	100

Source: Primary data

INTERPRETATION:

From the above table it is interpreted that 58% of the respondents were satisfied with the door delivery and 18% of the respondents were highly satisfied with the door delivery and 12% of the respondents were neutral with the door delivery and 10% of the respondents were highly dissatisfied with the door delivery and 2% of the respondents were with door delivery.

TABLE-12 SHOWING THE CUSTOMER SATISFICATION WITH THE SERVICE COST

Service cost	Frequency	Percent
Highly satisfied	28	28
Satisfied	48	48
Neutral	16	16
Dissatisfied	3	3
Highly dissatisfied	5	5
Total	100	100

Source: primary data

INTERPRETATION:

From the above table it is interpreted that 48% of the respondents were satisfied with the service cost and 28% of the respondents were highly satisfied with the service cost and 16% of the respondents were neutral with the service cost and 5% of the respondents were highly dissatisfied with the service cost and 3% of the respondents were dissatisfied with the service cost.

CHI-SQUARE ANALYSIS

To find out the Relationship between the Gender of the respondents and choosing the CHANDRA HONDA auto.

AIM: To test the Hypothesis from the given data using Chi-square Analysis

- HO- There is no significance difference between gender and choosing HONDA auto.
- H1- There is significance difference between gender and choosing HONDA auto

TABLE-13 TO FIND OUT THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE GENDER AND THE SERVICE MAN WAS ABLE TO UNDERSTAND THE VECHILE ISSUES

Chi-Square Tests	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	7.41810029	3	0.05
Likelihood Ratio	8.818710247	3	0.03
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.390604435	1	0.06
N of Valid Cases	100		

INTERPRETATION

Since significant value is greater than 0.05 accept null hypothesis. So there no significant association between gender and the service man was able to understand the vehicle issue.

- Chi-square test to find out the difference between age of the respondents and the reason for choosing the HONDA auto.
- HO- There is no significance difference between age and choosing HONDA auto.
- H1- There is significance difference between age and choosing HONDA auto

TABLE-14 TO FIND OUT THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE AGE AND THE LEVEL OF INSURANCE POLICY

Chi-Square Tests	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	65.00736954	16	7.34
Likelihood Ratio	65.23561882	16	6.70
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.575322332	1	0.44
N of Valid Cases	100		

INTERPRETATION

Since significant value is greater than 0.05 accept null hypothesis. So there no significant association between age and the level of insurance policy.

FINDINGS, SUGGESTION, AND CONCLUSION FINDINGS

- It is found that majority (75%) of the respondents are male
- It is found that majority (36%) of the respondents are aged between 18-25 years
- It is found that majority (41%) of the respondents have Up to 12th as a qualification .
- It is found that majority (46%) of respondents annual income were between 2-5 lakhs
- It is found that majority (63%) of the respondents were within the city

- It is found that majority (36%) of the respondents were satisfied with the total time taken
- It is found that majority (66%) of the company provides free service in half yearly
- It is found that majority (32%) of the respondents were neutral with the taking care of insurance policy
- It is found that majority (33%) of the respondents were satisfied with the customer care call centers
- It is found that majority (40%) of the respondents were some time availability in showroom
- It is found that majority (58%) of the respondents were satisfied with the door delivery
- It is found that majority (48%) of the respondents were satisfied with the service cost
- It is found that majority 0.05 accept null hypothesis. So there no significant association between gender and the service man was able to understand the vehicle issue.
- It is found that majority 0.05 accept null hypothesis So there no significant association between age and the level of insurance policy.
- CHANDRA HONDA can improve their service with better spare parts
- The dealer can try to reduce the service charge.
- After the service is done the customer is called after 10 to 15 days through Phone and is asked about their satisfaction about the servicing.
- Before accepting the vehicle, a mutually acceptable delivery time and date is
- Fixed with the customer

CONCLUSION

It is found that the dealer has to be little more assertive and attractive in their service no matter whether it's financial schemes. Sales promotions are excellent. More awareness should be created with the customer's regarding product utility. It is hoped that the finding and suggestion would enable the dealer to understand the performance level and other grey areas where things will have to be consolidated to hold a better market position.

SUGGESTIONS

- The following suggestion may be followed by the company to improve the sales and services
- The salesman in the service station has to be more friendly with their customer.

REFERENCE

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- [2] www.wikipedia.com

